

LAMBDA PROJECT: SCULPY

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GitHub: <https://github.com/CasperGuldbechNielsen/Sculpy>

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"It's supposed to be automatic, but actually
you have to push this button."

— John Brunner (*Stand on Zanzibar*, 1969)

Introduction

Sculpy is our product that we're very proud of. Though we could not manage to deliver a software which can be deployed, packed and handed over to our client, but it can function as a prototype and it is able to cope with all the basic tasks and perform satisfactorily. The tests seem to validate and certify this claim.

We deliberately aimed high, and set goals that were way beyond the reach of beginners, like us. We enjoy daunting challenges, and we kept finding inspirations in them, which boosted our confidence. Our vision and expectations written throughout the following report can be interpreted as a sign of the *can do* attitude.

We assume Sculpy to be a fair outcome of our efforts.

Vision for the project

Project Objectives

The principal objective of this semester project is to fully comprehend and apply the Unified Process framework which we have been learning since the first semester. Someday we'd all like to become software developer professionals. In order to achieve this goal, we shall follow the methods and processes taught to us in two major lectures: Software Design & Software Construction.

Our personal objective is to absorb essential skills for creating a well-designed and maintainable software product using C# programming language. As Larman suggests it is critical to think in objects (2005, p. 4), we do accept his recommendation and we decided to discover the object-oriented analysis and design (OOA/D). But how should we proceed? Larman summarizes the key methodology brilliantly: '*do the right thing (analysis), and do the thing right (design).*' (Ibid., p. 7).

We accepted a 'real-world' project proposal offered by a 'real-world' company, consequently our end product is to fulfil changing, genuine and realistic requirements which need to be analysed. We are eager to experience the connecting line from Business Analysis, Business Modelling to Implementation and Testing. The development plan, such as our strategy, standards and tactics will be formulated in accordance with the *agile project management approach* (Ibid., p. 674).

We expected to face the daunting challenge of satisfying our client's vital needs. Following the guidelines of our textbook on which practices and methods we ought to choose, it was settled that we would comply fully with the Unified Process (UP).

Larman points out that during the iterative and evolutionary development process the 'development starts before all the requirements are defined in detail' (Ibid. p. 18). As a well-defined time frame has been given for us to succeed and deliver a software product within, we did have the desire to choose a development process that includes less project failure and provides early feedback. Larman describes UP as a process which combines the best practices into an iterative, well-documented and risk-driven development (Ibid. p. 18).

We got to the point of realizing what the *right thing to do* is, now we shall step further to *doing the thing right*.

Our team chose to utilize other agile methods along UP, turning the software development process into a more incremental and iterative one. As a conclusion stated by the Agile Alliance, revisiting the same artefacts, repeating the software development activities help our project becoming agile and iterative (Glossary 2015), it encouraged us to organize 'daily scrum' meetings which took place through timeboxed iterations.

We abided by the practices of the Agile Modelling throughout the scrum meetings in order to support our better understanding. Throughout our daily scrum meetings we've been encouraged to use the whiteboard for sketching UML diagrams, as their value assessed and considered as necessary support of building a strong architecture to solve user-case driven requirements (Rumbaugh et al. 1999, p. 8).

Summarizing the main arguments for our future development process, we follow the professional advice and enforce the principles and guidelines behind the Agile Manifesto (Beck et al. 2001a, 2001b). Our key will be adapting to change in general:

'Responding to change over following a plan'

'Welcome changing requirements, even late in development. Agile processes harness change for the customer's competitive advantage.'

Problem definition

As each group must do so, we use the following problem definition, according to our Project Charter (Henriksen and Eftekhari, 2016):

"How can Unified Process (UP), C# Programming and Relational Databases be used for development and implementation of a minor single user IT system?"

Sub-problem definitions:

- *"Is it possible to deliver a product at the end of each iteration?"*
- *"Is it possible to adapt to changing requirements during the development process?"*

Analysis of Business

What is a business organization? During our Software Design lectures that, essentially, was the first question we sought to answer to. We discovered and all agreed, that basically an organization is a group of people or a business entity formed to achieve a certain and a common goal.

Our project report's outline might suggest, that the following part does not belong to the inception phase, however it truly does. '*UP is very flexible and open*' (Larman 2005, p. 18). In our terms, it is absolutely necessary to present the business architecture and the basic structure of the *organization*, which is going to be our client.

There are some questions to be answered prior to any kind of conceptualization of the potential Information System we are likely to develop: What is the vision for this project, shall we buy it or build it, and foremost is it feasible?

The artifacts following the introduction of our client's company will help us to envision the product scope and the business case (Ibid., p. 48).

The company

We all agreed upon the topic of this project on the subject of "*sculptures*" on the same day, when it has been presented to us on 23rd February 2016, by Eva Bøje Nielsen.

Eva described her *one-man-company*: she is a conservator-restorer dedicated to outdoor artistic and cultural artifacts: monuments, facades, fountains and reliefs (*further referenced along this report just as 'sculptures' for the reason of simplicity*).

She feels responsible for the preservation and restoration of our domestic cultural heritage. With about 10 years of field-experience she managed build a vast database of outdoor sculptures which are owned by the Municipality of Copenhagen.

In the database quite likely all relevant information can be found about the sculptures. Which materials they are made of, where they can be found at and what their name is. It is possible to add notes of inspections to the individual sculpture entries. Examining the sculptures visually by checking their overall state, monitoring and documenting their condition or any damages found as well as recommending treatments for them.

She is to accomplish the following ultimate goals: to ensure the damages being repaired and to prevent any further degradation of the sculptures.

By reporting her recommendations and remarks to the municipality, they discuss the most urgent cases, estimating overall costs and planning the jobs needed to be done. She does minor fixes herself too, or she offers contractor companies from her network for more substantial and complex projects.

Regarding her future perspectives: she would like to see possible partners instead of contenders and competitors in this market, furthermore organizing workshops or long-term collaborations for complex conservation projects.

She is open to expand her activities beyond Copenhagen, most likely over Scandinavia and somehow, sometime might involve the tourists into the process.

Business Analysis Artifacts

"A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers and captures value."

(Osterwalder and Pigneur 2009, p. 14)

The company of our client was presented by Eva (*notes shown in Appendix 2*), which was the first time that it was introduced to us. We took notes, and asked questions in order to fully understand and to be able to model and illustrate the basic structure of her business activities.

An artefact belongs to the terminology of UP (Larman 2005, p. 34), we can call 'artefact' any work-related products, such as our source code, database model, or all the diagrams and documents we create. The purpose of creating these collections and models is to *understand*, rather than document any target of them.

Another term of UP is 'discipline', it shows all activities we may go through to produce a particular set of activities and artifacts (UPEDU, 2014a). Thus the following artifacts belong to the Business Modeling Discipline.

The Business Model Canvas

We need to describe our client's business model as simply as possible. The Business Model Canvas (BMC) (*shown in Figure 1*) offers a concept that allows us to do so (Osterwalder and Pigneur 2009, p. 15).

The BMC has 9 building blocks:

- **Customer Segments:** it defines the groups of people or organizations an enterprise aims to reach and serve. In our case, the customer is the Copenhagen Municipality, more precisely the department which is responsible for managing the outdoor sculptures owned by the city.
- **Value Propositions:** it describes the products and services that create value for the Customer Segments. The service of the company is creating its value at the same time: keeping the sculptures last longer (protecting the cultural heritage).
- **Channels:** it describes how the company reaches its Customer Segments to deliver a Value Proposition. Meetings between the municipality and the company take place regularly.
- **Customer Relationships:** it illustrates what type of relationship the company establishes with its Customer Segments. A co-operative partnership has been developed during the years passed.
- **Revenue Streams:** it represents the cash-flow generated from each Customer Segment. Each and every job done and paid by the contract between the company and the municipality.
- **Key Resources:** it describes the assets required to make the business work. It's not just the tools and 'hardware' to manipulate the data with, but also the intellectual capital, the professional experience as a human resource.
- **Key Activities:** it illustrates the most important things the company must do to make the business work. Our client does inspections, planned or ad-hoc based, when the current state and condition of the sculptures get logged. During the meeting sessions comments and

remarks are presented, and according to the common agreement the fixing jobs are made or outsourced by our client.

- **Key Partners:** it defines the network of partners that make the business model work. The alliance between the company and the municipality as a buyer-supplier relation, and the strategic partnership with some contractors.
- **Cost Structure:** it describes all costs incurred during the business operation. There are fixed costs, like banking and legal fees, and there are marginal (variable) costs, like the price of the tools and materials used for restoration jobs.

Figure 1

SWOT Analysis

With the BMC we managed to get a birds-eye view at the business structure of the company, it is necessary to analyse and explore the wider context of how our prospective Information System will fit into its business strategy.

What is *strategy*? Considering the different, even some historical approaches by Cadle and Yates (2008, p. 16-17.) we can state that strategy is kind of a plan, a way for achieving something. It is vital that we comprehend the strategy of the company for which we are developing our new system. A possible way to do so, is analysing the business circumstances with investigating the internal and external environment. There are many analytical tools of examining the current situation (Ibid., p. 20), like some well-known as the SWOT analysis, the PESTEL analysis, the Balanced Business Scorecard and the Boston Consulting Group matrix.

We settled on the SWOT analysis (*shown in Figure 2*), which identifies the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that face the company. Strengths and Weaknesses are internal factors, Opportunities and Threats are considered as external factors. Without a strategic internal action to eliminate some of the weaknesses, the opportunities might be taken by our client's competitors.

Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Vast database of outdoor sculptures• 10 years of field experience• Low operational cost• First one who started	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Small income,• "One-man" company• Old inflexible database• Can't do all-round fixes
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Upcoming market• Domestic level (churches, private, municipalities)• International level (Scandinavia)• Rising awareness of cultural heritage• Future vision: as online tourist app• Co-op with other conservators	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Swedish competitors• Unprofessional cleaning companies offer cheap substitute services• Low budget by municipalities for this purpose• Other conservators unwilling to co-op

Figure 2

How could a potential strategy be defined? From our perspective by developing a new Information System for the company by which it will be much easier to manipulate the existing data. We aim to eliminate one entity from the weaknesses (*old inflexible database*), in order to have our client take the opportunities by herself, rather than the competitors in the market.

Porter's Five Forces

Can our Information System generate a competitive advantage on the market? It is imperative to investigate the macroeconomic environment which the company exist within. Beyond just the birds-eye view, it is necessary to formulate the possible strategy considering the competition in the whole market.

Porter's five forces model (*shown in Figure 3*) is the key of strategy formulation when we look at the macro-environment.

Figure 3

- **Threat of new entry:** if the market seems attractive and there's only a weak competition, newcomers will want to enter the market. Based on the presentation day (*notes shown in*

Appendix 2), we acknowledged that quite a few entrants seemed to be active, and showing interest. They're mostly unqualified for such a precision demanding jobs (cleaning companies and masons) and their competitive edge is offering a low-cost service.

- **Threat of substitutes:** based on the current state of our knowledge, there isn't any substitute services with functional similarity yet.
- **Suppliers:** the uniqueness of the products, tools and materials used for the conservation determine this power. We haven't got any info related.
- **Buyers:** the bargaining power of the buyer is very strong, due to its monopolistic circumstance. The municipality may break the contract, and award another company from the new entrants.
- **The competition:** in our opinion (we consider the most activities of conservation as highly skilled- and high precision-demanding job) there is no fierce competition, nor rivalry yet.

According to Porter (Cadle and Yates 2008, p. 24) it is essential to deal with the competition when the strategy is formulated. We have to consider all five forces determining the market. As a small company which has slightly weak bargaining power in any sense, we shall support it when the company is facing the threats.

In order to gain competitive advantage, we can empower our client with a useful tool, an Information System with some modern components. An application which we can enhance the company to differentiate itself with, to distinguish its service from the competition's offerings.

Business Product Vision

Following the analysis of the business and its environment, we shall present our ideas about the system we likely to develop in the future. A general statement of what we aim, expect or hope to achieve in the forthcoming process.

The 'Vision' is a requirements artefact offered by the UP (Larman 2005, p. 58). It summarizes the high level requirements, the business case and the big ideas for the project.

As the iterative and incremental development process demands, we have been refining all of our artifacts, especially after the 2nd meeting with our client (*see Appendix 3*), hence we only kept the

finalized version we agreed upon, and thus only them are going to be presented throughout our report.

Vision Statement

“Sculpy” aspires to equip its one and only client with a powerful app. We protect yesterday’s heritage with tomorrow’s technology.

Our client is most likely the one who has dedicated her career to protecting Denmark’s most endangered artwork, the outdoor sculptures. Our cultural heritage is vulnerable to vandalism and exposed to Mother Nature.

Perhaps there aren’t too many conservators in Scandinavia who’d like to take responsibility for organizing and arranging renovation works on exterior statues and monuments, but why not be the one who’s thriving in the market, as an early adopter of the most recent technology?

Our goal is quite simple: to provide our client with a tool that keeps her database up-to-date and a valuable software product for proposing restoration plans towards the municipality.

Positioning

Problem statement

The problem:	All the information is stored in an old, inflexible database system, held in Microsoft Access and Microsoft Excel format, which keeps track of each of the sculptures’ general information, the damages, repairing and cleaning notes.
Affecting:	Her entire workflow, as her “system” has gotten old and does not comply with today’s standards. The reaction time of the municipality, as they cannot see any up-to-date information and the database without her handing out the entire data.
Impacting:	Her productivity is low. Manipulating the data consumes time. Her solution is out-of-date which raises concerns about back-up, security, flexibility and usability.
Successful solution:	To create a system which conforms to modern standards, that has more intuitive user interface, works on mobile platforms and has cloud based backup solution.

Product position statement

For:	Eva Bøje Nielsen
Who:	Needs to register the sculptures' overall condition on the spot. Needs an option for presenting the treatment plans for the municipality based on different filtering and sorting criteria. Needs to have a better overview and searching option for all the sculptures. Needs to have an option for inserting pictures into the database.
The product:	Sculpy
That:	Provides flexible searching and fast retrieval of information needed.
Unlike:	The database with frontend she has now.
Our product:	A tool that makes the control of the data more flexible, and has a user friendly interface.

Stakeholder description

Stakeholder summary

Name	Description	Responsibilities
Eva Bøje Nielsen	The one and only user of the system.	Maintaining the database by using the system.

User environment

Eva Bøje Nielsen is riding her bike around Copenhagen, monitoring the sculptures' condition. Her mission is to log inspections by investigating the overall state of the outdoor monuments. She spends the required time for inputting the damages to the system that have been discovered on the spot, and selects a recommended way of treatment. She optionally defines the frequency or timeframe of required check-ups. After she's done, goes to the next sculpture planned to visit. Eva uses her tablet when she is out in the field and can also use her desktop at home.

Product overview

Needs and features

"Features are behavioral functions a system can *do*. They should pass this linguistic test: *The system does <feature X>.*" (Larman 2005, p. 113)

Need	Priority	Features	Description
Database	High	Data processing	Operations performed by the system in order to Create, Retrieve, Update and Delete information
Portability	High	Platform Customization	The system needs to be compatible with multiple platforms (i.e. tablet, PC, phone).
Graphical User Interface (GUI)	High	Graphical Representation	The system needs a graphical user interface, which is light, flexible and easy to use.
Auto-suggested search	Medium	Data Reasoning	The system offers data entries similar to user input
Adding photos	Medium	Data Processing	The system is capable of adding images to relevant data entries
Draw reports	High	Document Integration	The system is capable of exporting reports based on inspections.
Map	Medium	Location Tracking	The system is capable to determine the user's location.
Spell check	Low	Linguistic Correction	The system offers grammatical corrections.
Cloud back-up	High	Data Migration	The system is capable of data synchronization with the server.

Other product requirements

Supplementary Specifications

FURPS+	Requirement	Priority	Description
Functionality	Security	High	All usage requires user authentication
Usability	Consistency in UI	High	Having high regard for outdoor usage: contrast of colors. Allow easy and quick access to main features.
Reliability	Recoverability	Medium	Cloud back-up in case of any hardware or software failure
	Accuracy	High	Appropriate level of detail and data precision. Modifications are reflected accurately in the data
Performance	Efficiency	Medium	Low-cost operation: student subscription to Microsoft Azure server, database and WebAPI
	Availability	Medium	Main features are available without internet connection
Supportability	Compatibility	High	Available on every device that runs Windows 10 (Desktop, Mobile, Xbox, IoT, Surface Hub, HoloLens)
+	Legal	Medium	Open sourced code on GitHub

The Supplementary Specifications appear in the Vision artefact. The reason why they're listed here instead of the Requirements subsection is quite simple. We concluded that the *FURPS+* model summarizes the quality characteristics which we captured before we went deeply into detail concerning the requirements. In our opinion, organizing these specifications here gives better structure for the artefact and easier read for someone who would like to join the project. This idea has been confirmed by Larman too. (Ibid., p. 111)

The Project – Sculpy

Project Establishment

We analyzed the business environment by investigating both the internal and the external conditions. Then we examined the strengths and weaknesses of the company, its possible opportunities and the market with the competitors. Based on our inspections and analysis we outlined a futuristic and optimistic vision for our client.

Showing an ideal direction we reached the part where we would establish our team, for one purpose: to carry out the project.

In the following sections we shall introduce how we are approaching the development of our system.

Human Resources

What makes a great team? A perfect mixture of skills. Each and all of us have been involved with the entire process from the planning and sketching, along the drawing and constructing until the coding. Everyone participated of the production of all the models, artifacts and diagrams. To make our proceedings effective we decided to appoint everyone a role, and nominate them with different responsibilities in accordance with our experience. They're more likely 'responsibilities' rather than just 'roles'.

Name	Role	Description
Casper	Lead Architect	Define what components are involved in the product and how they get to interact with each other.
Daniel	Lead Developer	Develop and program, code reviewer.
Istvan	Lead Writer	Scrum Master and Microsoft Azure Resource manager.
Toke	UX Designer	Improve User Experience, usability and accessibility.

Name	Email	GitHub	Trello
Casper	casp674d@edu.easj.dk	@CasperGuldbechNielsen	@caspd
Daniel	simionescu_dany@yahoo.com	@Daniel-Simionescu	@danielsimionescu1
Istvan	istvan.marki@gmail.com	@ystvan	@istvanmarki
Toke	tokefrostholm@gmail.com	@TFrostholm	@tokefrostholmrmussen

Technology Resources

As students enrolled at Erhervsakademi Sjælland, we are provided with many subscriptions and licenses through DreamSpark at no cost for professional-level developer and designer tools.

- **Visual Studio 2015 Enterprise:** a software application, an IDE (*Integrated Development Environment*) from Microsoft that is used to develop computer programs.
- **GitHub:** a web-based repository hosting service for version control and collaboration. A version control is a system that records changes to a file over time (*i.e. the source code*). It allows us to revert back to a previous state, compare changes, and see who last modified something. A perfect tool to work on a project together.
- **Microsoft Azure:** a cloud computing platform and infrastructure for building, deploying, managing and hosting services and applications like: *App Service, Cloud Service, SQL server and database, Blob Storage* and so forth.
- **Microsoft Visio 2016:** a software for drawing diagrams, part of the Microsoft Office family.
- **Trello:** a collaboration tool that helps us organize our project into boards. More detailed information is described at Project Management section.
- **OneNote and OneDrive:** *OneNote* is kind of a digital notebook. It helped us organize our project, unlike Trello it allows you a free-form information input without enforced page layout or structure (handwritten or typed, inserting pictures, diagrams, also audio commentaries, video clips and so forth). It saves information in pages organized into sections within notebooks. We don't need to explicitly save our work, it saves data automatically as we work. We hosted the notebook file in Microsoft's cloud storage: *OneDrive*.
- **PoP:** free prototyping tool

Microsoft Azure

As it's been described in the Vision artefact previously, both the *database* and the *cloud back-up* features have high priority, moreover we included the *recoverability* and the *efficiency* as requirements for our system.

Why cloud and why exactly did we choose Azure? Cloud is all about *sharing* resources in order to stop wasting them. We are not intend to cover more about cloud computing through this report. From our point of view the main benefits of choosing Azure is far more relevant (Documentation Center, 2016a).

- **Pay as you go:** using Microsoft Azure we only need to pay for the resources that our applications are using.
- **Scalability on demand:** we can just simply adjust our rate, in case we need more data storage for example, and it is easy to avoid paying for an empty storage which we may never use. 'Pay as you grow' approach to respond more quickly to changes in our client's needs: for our Web app we can specify the number of processors without any additional coding.
- **Geo-replicated backup store:** our data is stored in geo-replicated storage which maintains 6 encrypted copies of our data across two Azure datacenters, it means 99.9% availability even when a natural disaster takes place.
- **Fast deployment:** Azure allows us to directly deploy our WebAPI from Visual Studio (see Figure 5), in addition it is possible to deploy from a variety of source control as well (see Figure 4).

Figure 5

Figure 4

- **Flexibility:** Azure allows us to even run Visual Studio in the cloud. Just imagine it, we can deploy a virtual machine in the cloud with Visual Studio running on it! We don't even need our own laptop to work in our project, just any machine with fast internet connection.

V12 Logical Server and the database

We managed to obtain a subscription to Azure, called 'Azure Pass' which is worth \$100 monthly. This subscription allows us to choose exclusive services and the latest technology from the year 2016 (Documentation Center, 2016b).

Basic			
	DTUs	MAX STORAGE PER DB	PRICE ¹
B	5	2 GB	~kr31/mo

Standard			
	DTUs	MAX STORAGE PER DB	PRICE ¹
S0	10	250 GB	~kr95/mo
S1	20	250 GB	~kr189/mo
S2	50	250 GB	~kr472/mo
S3	100	250 GB	~kr944/mo

Premium			
	DTUs ²	MAX STORAGE PER DB	PRICE ¹
P1	125	500 GB	~kr2,926/mo
P2	250	500 GB	~kr5,853/mo
P4	500	500 GB	~kr11,706/mo
P6	1000	500 GB	~kr23,411/mo
P11	1750	1 TB	~kr44,060/mo

Figure 6

SQL databases are available in Basic, Standard and Premium service tiers. Each service tier offers different levels of performance and capabilities to support database workloads. The 'Standard' option is recommended for most cloud applications so that we selected the first level 'S0' (shown in Figure 6). The levels within the tiers differ only in the number of Database Transaction Unit (DTU). This unit represents the relative power of the databases. Since we are going to use one single server with one relational database, understanding these measures are irrelevant in our case. As described in our Vision

artefact, the 'Adding photos' feature listed as medium priority we decided in favor of the slightly bigger storage.

Moreover with using the 'Standard' service we managed to select the *Geo-Replication* service. It allows us to configure secondary databases in different data center regions. Our primary server and database

Figure 7

located in North-Europe and the secondary *back-up* is located in West Europe (shown in Figure 7).

It means almost zero downtime even if the datacenter suffers permanent loss caused by natural disasters, catastrophic human errors or malicious acts. Besides these events, this option is useful when our primary database fails, or needs to be taken offline.

Microsoft Azure Storage

What is Azure Storage? (Documentation Center, 2016c). It is the cloud storage solution for modern applications that rely on durability, availability and scalability to meet the needs of our client. As almost every services provided by Azure, Storage is highly scalable, even if we store small amount of data or

hundreds of terabytes we only need to pay for the data we're using. It supports a variety of operating systems and languages, so as applications based on the C# language and the .NET Framework. Storage also exposes data resources via REST APIs, which complies exactly with our plan: sending and receiving data via HTTP/HTTPS.

The reason we considered using and inquired into Storage is very simple: it is not supported to upload images to Azure SQL anymore.

Azure Storage provides four services: Blob, Table, Queue and File storage. Since we require to manage multimedia objects we agreed upon the Blob service. BLOB is an abbreviation of Binary Large Object.

Figure 8

A quite simple presentation of the Blob service (shown in Figure 8):

- **Storage account:** it is a scalable, durable cloud storage, backup and recovery solution for any data, big or small. Can be found under the Data + Storage section in Azure's marketplace. The name of our account (Sculpy) forms the *subdomain* of our object's unique URL address. In our case the endpoint of our account is <https://sculpy.blob.core.windows.net>
- **Container:** a container provides a grouping of a set of blobs. All blobs must be in a container. We have two containers 'images' container (<https://sculpy.blob.core.windows.net/images>) to store photos taken during the usage of our app by doing inspections and 'sculptures' container (<https://sculpy.blob.core.windows.net/sculptures>) to store avatar images for the sculptures.
- **Blob:** a file of any type and size, each and every blob object has a unique URL, in our case this is proved very useful, as discussed later on. (<https://sculpy.blob.core.windows.net/images/1.jpg>).

Azure App Service

Azure App service (Documentation Center, 2016d) is a cloud service that integrates previously separated services (Web Apps, API Apps, Logic Apps, Azure Websites and Azure Mobile Services) basically everything we need to build web and mobile apps for any platform and any device.

Due to the following benefits, we agreed to choose this service:

- **No migration process:** we can bring our existing API as-is, there's no need to change any of the code to deploy and publish to Azure App Service
- **Simple access control:** we can protect our API from unauthenticated access with no changes to our code. Azure provides built-in authentication services. It supports identity providers like Facebook, Twitter, Google and Microsoft account.
- **Visual Studio integration:** by installing the Azure SDK 2.8.1 for .NET many dedicated tools will be available to deploy, debug and managing our API app (*shown in Figures 9 and 10*).

Figure 9

Figure 10

Group Contract

It is the duty of each and every one of us to follow what we agreed upon by the group establishment. Any violations have serious consequences.

The rules to adhere are:

- We are expected to show up for scheduled school days and group meetings. Exceptions apply within 2 hours' notice time in advance.
- We have to give advice or help to each other.
- We have to share! Keep the team aware of everybody's state and advance.
- We have to communicate through all platforms, Facebook group is preferred.
- We have to respect and discuss all ideas and opinions.
- We have to respect all deadlines from both school and the team.

List of Risks and Management Plan

The following artefact represents our identification of the possible risks we likely to face during the project. Based on a thorough revision of Lemon's Risk List (2002, p. 5) we created our own version.

The 'Probability' is a scale ranked from 1 to 10 (*10 is the highest chance of occur*), the 'Impact' (*Low-Medium-High*) shows the level of the given risk's impact, and the 'Mitigation Strategy' describes the plan to live with or avoid/transfer the risk.

Probability	Description	Impact	Mitigation Strategy
8	Group member sickness, or lack of attendance	High	Redistribution of assignments, worst case scenario: re-group
5	Loss of data	High	Version control, back-up files using cloud services
7	Lack of database systems knowledge	Medium	Exchange our experiences, consult with supervisors
6	Miss the deadline	Medium	Revision of iteration plans, responding swiftly to changes

Project Management

Project Management (UPEDU, 2014b) is the discipline of planning, organizing and managing our resources to reach the successful completion of our goals and objectives through the project. Basically it is the 'know-how' of working together in order to get the job done. Project Management is the key tool for implementing a strategy.

Firstly, we will focus on managing our 'human resources'.

Trello

Trello is a web-based project management application, using the Kanban-schema. However we changed it a bit. We are using cards, organized to lists within our board (shown in Figure 11).

Figure 11

- **Backlog:** this list holds all scheduled tasks ('cards'). It's a space to hold ideas and a place to develop ideas into actionable items until they're ready to be started. After a deadline is specified, description edited it can be moved to the 'Next'.
- **Next:** it contains tasks ready to be completed, listed in order with most important tasks at the top, as determined by the scrum master. Tasks may be assigned to individual developers at this stage.

- **In progress:** Once a developer starts a task, it will be moved to this list to show that work is progressing.
- **Staged:** After a developer's task is complete and ready to be reviewed by the scrum master or client, it will be moved here. If changes are needed, move the task back to 'Next' with comments. Otherwise, move the task to 'Approved'.
- **Approved:** When a card is completed and approved, then the reviewer should leave a LGTM (Looks Good to Me) comment and move the card to the Approved list.

When more work needs to be done, the scrum master/reviewer leaves a comment describing the additional changes needed. If a response is required, then use a @mention (*tagging members*). The card should be moved back to the Next list. If priority is an issue, it should be labelled as urgent.

Daily Scrum-logs

It is 'team plenum diary', short reminders, sketches and brief meeting logs. Each day spent working on the project recorded as memos (*shown in Figure 12*), it is very helpful to compare the original *planned* and the *achieved* tasks later on.

The image shows a screenshot of a project log with the following content:

- Prototyping (PoP => pictures taken)
- Domain Model
- [Day 19 \(Thursday 7/04\)](#)
- Data Modelling
- Mock-up in Illustrator
- WEEK 8.**
- [Day 20 \(Monday 11/04\)](#)
- Mock-up in Illustrator
- Inserting data to tables
- ER Model is finished
- [Day 21 \(Tuesday 12/04\)](#)
- Altering database, inserting data
- Mock-up in Illustrator (editing/creating new pages: add/edit sculpture, settings, inspections)
- UC check-up based on "Writing Effective Use Cases - A. Cockburn"
- [Day 22 \(Thursday 14/04\)](#)
- Core Architecture Model
- Mock-up finished
- Project documentation: project report
- WEEK 9.**
- [Day 23 \(Tuesday 19/04\)](#)
- Interaction Diagrams
- System Sequence Diagram
- Class Diagram
- Implementing UC2 - CRUD logs
- Azure WebApp + server + database setup in the cloud
- Preparing for 2nd meeting with our stakeholder
- [Day 24 \(Wednesday 20/04\)](#)
- WEEK 13.**
- [Day 34 \(Tuesday 17/5\)](#)
- Istvan: SelectedInspection, SelectedInspectioEdit
- Toke: add new Inspection
- Daniel: CRUD sculptures
- [Day 35 \(Wednesday 18/5\)](#)
- Splitting the project report: ALL
- Casper, Toke: Diagrams
- Toke: crud inspections
- Daniel: TEST, adding confirmation DialogBoxes
- Istvan: report
- [Day 36 \(Thursday 19/5\)](#)
- Casper: diagrams
- Toke: crud inspections
- Daniel: TESTING
- Istvan: report
- 3rd meeting with Eva
- WEEK 14.**
- [Day 37 \(Monday 23/5\)](#)
- Istvan: report
- Casper: diagrams (they kick ass)
- Toke: report + confirmation boxes
- Daniel: HR use cases
- [Day 38 \(Tuesday 24/5\)](#)
- Toke: Report
- Casper: Diagrams, report
- Daniel: fixing, polishing
- Istvan: report

Figure 12

One Note

It has been described previously what OneNote is in the *Technology Resources* section.

Figure 13

Trello and OneNote are interconnected in the way we use them. We defined colorful tabs, separated and named each one of them by the development phases. For presentational purpose, the 'Inception Phase' tab (shown in Figure 13) consisted of artifacts like the Business Model Canvas, the SWOT Analysis and the Vision artefact. Since the notebook is shared amongst the developers (team members) and stored in OneDrive with the auto-sync and auto-save function it is possible to see our progress in real time, even if we work from home remotely.

All changes can be traced, due to the built-in option of the software, it indicates every modification by the acronym of the developer's name.

One of the greatest benefit of the software is that it allows us to use free-form information input, and the whole notebook can be exported to a variety of file formats (PDF, Word, image, table and so forth).

GitHub

The GitHub repository hosting service has been mentioned as well as OneNote in the Technology Resources section, so that in the following paragraph we intend to describe from the Project Management point of view, how we are actually using the GitHub Flow (GitHub Guides, 2013).

GitHub flow is a lightweight, branch-based workflow. It is recommended for teams like us where deployments are made in regular basis and quite frequently.

As we sign up a developer by adding him to a specific card on Trello in order to implement a *feature*, it is very important to create a branch prior to any coding. It is a safe way to experiment, commit any changes knowing that the *master* branch won't be affected (*shown in Figure 14*). These branches won't be merged until it's ready to be reviewed by some of the other collaborating developers.

Whenever a developer makes changes and saves it, the changes are ready to be committed and pushed. Each commit has an associated message, a short description why the changes were made or what had been done. This creates traceability, it allows us to roll back changes if a bug is found, or we decide to head in a different direction.

Figure 14

After a feature is implemented during the development process in the separate branch, a developer can open a pull request. It means the group will be notified through GitHub and can see all the changes would be merged if they accept the request. A pull request allows us to see if there are any conflicts. However, it is not recommended, but in urgent cases a developer can also confirm his own pull request. Once an opened pull request is confirmed and accepted, the separate branch will be merged into the master.

Iterative Development

The key practice of the UP method is the iterative development (Larman 2005, p. 19). Iterative development is described as a *'lifecycle approach'*, where the whole process is organized into short, fixed-length (timeboxed) periods, called *iterations*.

The system grows incrementally iteration by iteration, as a result of these iterations we get to a deliverable, but incomplete system.

We are going to examine what we have planned, achieved and failed during the iterations, investigate the iteration plans, risks, challenges we faced and compare them with our results. (*See more at 'Evaluating the Iterations' sections*).

Overall Plan

As we started our development process we established a plan (*shown in Figure 15*). As we stated in the

Figure 15

'Project Objectives' introduction section, and the time has proven to us: *Responding to change over following a plan'* (Beck et al. 2001a). We did not use this artefact.

Quality Factors

We have quality goals for our development effort (Marciniak 1994, p. 961). As defined in the 'Supplementary Specifications' section from our Vision artefact, we focus on quality factors connected to our desired features.

Quality Factor	Description
<i>Usability</i>	Effort required to develop a user friendly GUI
<i>Portability</i>	Effort required to develop an application compatible with variety of devices
<i>Efficiency</i>	Effort required to keep the operational costs low
<i>Reliability</i>	Effort required to use cloud services for secure back-up storage

Inception

Requirements

According to Larman (2005, p. 48) the purpose of the inception phase is not to define all the requirements. Most of the requirements occur during the elaboration phase.

Most of the requirements have been defined in the Vision and the Supplementary Specification artifact already.

Use Cases

Cockburn (2001, p. 21) divides the energy of writing use cases into four stages:

- **Actors and Goals:** list what actors and which their goals the system will support
- **Main Success Scenarios:** for the selected use cases write the stakeholders, trigger and the main success scenario. Make sure the system is delivering the interest of the stakeholders.
- **Failure Conditions:** brainstorm all the failures could occur during the process
- **Failure Handling:** write how the system is supposed to respond to each failure

Actors and Stakeholders

An actor is anything having a behaviour. It could be a person, a company or a computer program. According to Cockburn (2001, p. 28) the system under discussion (SuD) itself is an actor.

A secondary actor of a use case is an external actor which provides a service to the SuD. It might be a printer or a web service.

A stakeholder is someone with an interest of the use case, even if they never interact directly with the system. It means that every primary actor is a stakeholder as well.

Design Scope

The design scope is the extent of the system. All of our following use cases' scope is the 'system' itself.

Scenario

The sequence of interactions under certain conditions with the intent to achieve the primary actor's goal. The interactions start from the triggering action and they will continue until the goal is delivered or abandoned.

Goal levels

All of our use cases have 'blue' or 'sea-level': it means the level of greatest interest is the *user goal*.

Precondition, Success End Condition, Failure Protection

- **Precondition:** means that the given condition is known to be true, and not need to be checked again.
- **Success End Condition:** it states what interests of the stakeholders have been satisfied at the end of the use case
- **Failure Protection Condition:** it is a simple assertion about the state of the 'world' when the primary actor's goal has been abandoned

Use Case 1: CRUD sculptures

Brief Description

This use Case describes and directs operations for Creating, Retrieving, Updating, Deleting sculptures.

Actors

There are two actors for this use case which are:

- User (Primary actor)
- SuD (System under Discussion/Design, actor)
- SKULPY Resource Group on Azure (WebAPI, V12 logical server and database as a secondary actor)

Triggers

User selects operations explicitly using the System's interface

Goal level

User-goal level ("blue" or "sea level")

Design Scope

System (UWP sculpture database application, SuD)

Stakeholders and interests

User (Primary actor): to have a fast and reliable way of managing sculptures.

Precondition

User's device is connected to the internet.

User has been validated and logged into the system.

Success End Condition

All verified and confirmed amendments to the data has been saved successfully.

Failure Protection Condition

None.

Failed End Protection

None.

Main success scenario

User is able to Create, Retrieve, Update and Delete sculptures in the database.

DESCRIPTION	Step	Action
	1.	System displays repository
	2.	User performs repository operation
	3.	System updates repository
EXTENSIONS	Step	Branching Action
	2.A	User would like to create a new sculpture
	2.A.1	User chooses the option to create a new sculpture
	2.A.2	System displays sculpture creation form
	2.A.3	User enters required information and triggers create action
	2.A.4	System prompts user for requesting confirmation
	2.A.5	User confirms sculpture creation
	2.B	User would like to search for a sculpture
	2.B.1	User chooses the option to retrieve a sculpture
	2.B.2	System displays sculpture filtering and sorting form

	2.B.3	User enters required information and triggers filtering and sorting action
	2.B.4	System performs search action and presents information
	2.C	User would like to update a sculpture
	2.C.1	User chooses the option to retrieve a sculpture
	2.C.2	System displays sculpture filtering and sorting form
	2.C.3	User enters required information and triggers filtering and sorting action
	2.C.4	System performs search action and presents information
	2.C.5	User chooses the option to edit sculpture and performs change action
	2.C.6	System prompts user for requesting confirmation
	2.C.7	User confirms change execution
	2.D	User would like to delete a sculpture
	2.D.1	User chooses the option to retrieve a sculpture
	2.D.2	System displays sculpture filtering and sorting form
	2.D.3	User enters required information and triggers filtering and sorting action
	2.D.4	System performs search action and presents information
	2.D.5	User chooses the option for sculpture deletion
	2.D.6	System prompts user for requesting confirmation
	2.D.7	User confirms delete execution
	3.A	System interacts with SKULPY Resource Group on Azure

Special Requirements

None.

Technology and Data variations list

In case of unexpected hardware failure, user notes down her observations on paper and resume her goal afterwards on another device.

Open Issues

None.

Use Case 2: CRUD inspections

Brief Description

This use Case describes and directs operations for Creating, Retrieving, Updating, Deleting inspections.

Actors

There are two actors for this use case which are:

- User (Primary actor)
- SuD (System under Discussion/Design, actor)

- SKULPY Resource Group on Azure (WebAPI, V12 logical server and database as a secondary actor)

Triggers

User selects operations explicitly using the System's interface

Goal level

User-goal level ("blue" or "sea level")

Design Scope

System (UWP sculpture database application, SuD)

Stakeholders and interests

User (Primary actor): to have a fast and reliable way of monitoring the sculptures state and previous state by managing inspections.

Precondition

User's device is connected to the internet.
User has been validated and logged into the system.

Success End Condition

All verified and confirmed amendments to the data has been saved successfully.

Failure Protection Condition

None.

Failed End Protection

None.

Main success scenario

User is able to Create, Retrieve, Update and Delete inspections in the database.

DESCRIPTION	Step	Action
	1.	System displays repository
	2.	User performs repository operation
	3.	System updates repository
EXTENSIONS	Step	Branching Action
	2.A	User arrives at a sculpture and would like to create a new inspection
	2.A.1	User chooses the option to retrieve a sculpture
	2.A.2	System displays sculpture searching form
	2.A.3	User enters required information and triggers search action

	2.A.4	System performs search action and presents information
	2.A.5	User chooses the option to create a new inspection
	2.A.6	System displays inspection creation form
	2.A.7	User enters required information and triggers create action
	2.A.8	System prompts user requesting confirmation
	2.A.9	User confirms inspection creation
	2.B	User would like to search for an inspection
	2.B.1	User chooses the option to retrieve an inspection
	2.B.2	System displays inspection filtering form
	2.B.3	User enters required information and triggers search action
	2.B.4	System performs search action and presents information
	2.C	User would like to update an inspection
	2.C.1	User chooses the option to retrieve an inspection
	2.C.2	System displays inspection searching form
	2.C.3	User enters required information and triggers search action
	2.C.4	System performs search action and presents information
	2.C.5	User chooses the option to edit inspection and performs change action
	2.C.6	System prompts user requesting confirmation
	2.C.7	User confirms change execution
	2.D	User would like to delete an inspection
	2.D.1	User chooses the option to retrieve an inspection
	2.D.2	System displays inspection searching form
	2.D.3	User enters required information and triggers search action
	2.D.4	System performs search action and presents information
	2.D.5	User chooses the option for inspection deletion
	2.D.6	System prompts user requesting confirmation
	2.D.7	User confirms delete execution
	3.A	System interacts with Web Service/Microsoft Azure

Special Requirements

None.

Technology and Data variations list

In case of unexpected hardware failure, user notes down her observations on paper and resume her goal afterwards on another device.

Open Issues

None.

Use Case 3: Share data/Draw reports

Brief Description

This use Case describes and directs operations for creating and exporting reports based on inspections.

Actors

There are two actors for this use case which are:

- User (Primary actor)
- SuD (System under Discussion/Design, actor)
- SKULPY Resource Group on Azure (WebAPI, V12 logical server and database as a secondary actor)

Triggers

User selects operations explicitly using the System's interface

Goal level

User-goal level ("blue" or "sea level")

Design Scope

System (UWP sculpture database application, SuD)

Stakeholders and interests

User (Primary actor): to have a fast and reliable way of exporting reports based on inspections made previously and to present the reports to the given municipality.

Precondition

User's device is connected to the internet.
User has been validated and logged into the system.

Success End Condition

Requested reports have been successfully exported to required file format.

Failure Protection Condition

None.

Failed End Protection

None.

Main success scenario

User is able to draw reports based on the inspections made in the database.

DESCRIPTION	Step	Action
	1.	System displays repository
	2.	User performs repository operation
	3.	System exports data from repository
EXTENSIONS	Step	Branching Action
	2.A	User would like to draw a report
	2.A.1	User chooses the option to retrieve an inspection
	2.A.2	System displays inspection filtering form
	2.A.3	User enters required information and triggers search action
	2.A.4	System performs search action and presents information
	2.A.5	User selects required inspections to export data from
	2.A.6	User chooses the option for exporting data
	2.A.7	User performs exporting action
	2.A.8	System prompts user requesting confirmation
	2.A.9	User confirms execution

Special Requirements

None.

Technology and Data variations list

None.

Open Issues

None.

Use Case Diagram

As Larman states (2005, p. 90) "A simple use case diagram provides a succinct visual context diagram for the system, illustrating the external actors and how they use the system." – Which is exactly what we have done. We have taken the three key use cases from our project and made a visual overview on how the actor will interact with each of them (*shown in Figure 16*).

Figure 16

A use case diagram has the primary actor on the left side with the use cases in the middle and external actors or secondary actors (as a tax system) on the right side. There are association lines between the actors and use cases that are involved, meaning that if an actor is an active part of a use case it is connected by a line.

As our project only has one actor and no outside factors, our use case diagram is very simple and might even be redundant to create – however, as we strive to follow the principle of UP and its models and diagrams, we thought that a simple overview of the interaction between the actor and our use cases would be relevant to include particularly when considering the low time consumption it took to create.

GUI – PoP

To clarify our vision and to discuss our high-level ideas we developed a paper prototype during the Inception phase. A paper prototype is a low-fidelity (Lo-Fi) prototype, which means it is quick and easy to develop at a low cost. One advantage of Lo-Fi prototyping is that very few tools are needed – a simple pen and a piece of paper will do. Another advantage is that non-programmers can easily participate in the idea development process (Egger 2000).

We created our prototype through several sketching- and discussion sessions within our group, which meant that we did not waste time creating highly detailed design ideas because a sketch on paper or whiteboard can easily be discarded, when new ideas or discoveries are made. The product was a testable artefact that went through a few iterations before we decided on an overall plan for the interface and the interactions between UI elements.

Next, we developed our more High-Fidelity prototype meaning that we now focused on getting a more pixel-perfect mock-up that also focused on colours, distance between elements etc. We developed the mock-up in Adobe Illustrator before making it interactive and reading for testing using PoP.

Evaluating the Iterations

As the inception phase only consisted of one to two weeks, it was difficult to make real plans however we made a Gant chart to get a visual illustration of the work needed to be done. We also made use of Trello to organise when artefacts were done. We made no iteration plan, as the inception phase was so short that it seemed redundant to do so.

Elaboration

Domain Model

Figure 17

The domain model is (Larman 2005, p. 131) the most important classic model in OO analysis. The domain model shows concepts in the domain, or rather, conceptual classes in the scope. The domain model acts as the source of inspiration for many of the following artefacts made.

It is important to distance the domain model a bit from software objects, as the domain model is a presentation of real-situation conceptual classes. That being said, you will often create software classes based upon the conceptual classes in the domain model. As we have done with the CatalogOfSculptures and made the SculptureCatalogSingleton.

The domain model shows the conceptual classes and the relationship between these classes, this is shown by association lines and multiplicity; for example one sculpture can have one or many damage(s) as shown in circles in the picture below (shown in Figure 18).

Figure 18

Association lines are shown between objects in the domain model that have association. A sculpture can have a damage, a damage can have a treatment, but a sculpture cannot have a treatment. Multiplicity is shown to give an overview of how many objects of the same type that can occur at the same time. For example one sculpture can consist of many different materials. Therefore materials multiplicity is shown "1..*" – one to many.

We started our domain model after writing the use cases. We identified the conceptual classes based upon the use cases.

There is three ways of finding conceptual classes (probably more but these are the three most popular):

1. Reuse or modify existing model.
2. Use a category list.
3. Identify noun phrases.

We used the noun method to identify these conceptual classes. This involves reading through the use cases and underlining each noun found in the text. After all nouns are identified, they have to be considered as conceptual classes. This method is also called linguistic analysis.

The domain model helped us to identify conceptual classes, which eventually ended up as actual software classes or objects of the project. We used the domain model as an inspiration to creating the class diagram.

Entity Relationship Modelling

Once we had gathered the requirements for the database system, we began the design process. To get a clear understanding of the data and how the company will use it, we decided to create an Entity-

Relationship Model (ERM). Entity-Relationship modelling is a top-down approach, meaning that you start by identifying the entities and the relationships between them, unlike Normalization, which is a bottom-up approach, where the associations between attributes are identified prior to forming the tables and their relationships (Connolly & Begg 2004). After identifying the important data that makes up the entities, we added the attributes for each entity. We gave each entity a unique name and along with their respective properties, the entities represent a set of objects, that each is uniquely identifiable within the set. This means that even though an entity has a distinct set of attributes each entity-occurrence will have different values for the attributes.

By creating the ERM together as a group, we had the opportunity to discuss the overall design of our database together. This meant that we slowly moved towards a clear understanding and it helped all group members to participate fully and it ensured that we were all aware of what the tables contain and how they connect to each other.

Normalization

Normalization is a technique to reduce NULLs and to check that a database design does not contain redundant data, by ensuring that certain rules for each form (1NF, 2NF and 3NF) of the process are

Figure 19

not violated. Therefore, it is a process for deciding which attributes are grouped together in a relation so that all anomalies are removed to produce well-structured relations.

Even though Normalization is a different approach than ERM, it can also be used in conjunction with ERM. We used it alongside the ERM approach, and did not start Normalization until we had a clear understanding of our data. In order to find out if our tables would pass 1NF we translated the ERM into tables and ensured they passed the definition of 1NF, by making sure that any multivalued attributes had been removed so there was a single value (possibly null) at the intersection of each row and column of the table. A table in 2NF is one that is in 1NF and has no partial dependency, meaning that every non-key attribute is completely dependent on the entire primary key. This only applies to tables with composite keys and ensures that any non-key attribute depends on all parts of the composite key to be manipulated. We decided that reaching 3NF was not necessary for this project and therefore we did not spend any time trying to do so.

Core Architecture Diagram

To illustrate the overall architecture of our solution we created the Core Architecture Diagram (*shown in Figure 20*). The diagram shows how we have an MVVM application that connects to a Webservice through HTTP. The Webservice itself uses the Entity Framework data access technology to map the database and generate data access classes to our previously created database.

Figure 20

MVVM

The Model-View-ViewModel pattern is a design pattern that provides a separation of concerns i.e. isolating the user interface from the underlying business logic. MVVM consists of three main components: the model, the view and the view model. They each serve a specific role and interact with each other. However, one core element is that the View only “knows about” the ViewModel, and the ViewModel in turn only “knows about” the Model, while the Model as no idea about the ViewModel and the ViewModel is unaware of the View (*shown in Figure 21*).

Figure 21 – Relationships between the components of MVVM

One of the reasons why we decided to implement MVVM is because we wanted to ensure that the user interface could evolve independently of the logic. We knew that we would be concurrently designing the views and writing the necessary code so this pattern seemed just right because it is easy to redesign the UI of the application without touching the code. In addition, it also makes unit testing easier as the separated classes can be instantiated independently of the UI. If we had not used the MVVM pattern our code would be much more tightly coupled and thus more resistant to change and harder to maintain.

As shown in figure 19, our different views gets their data from their corresponding ViewModels through bindings and by invoking commands. Our ViewModels, which act as bridge between the View and the Model, handle all the view logic and notify the View when any information has changed. For example if we update the information for a Sculpture, the View notifies the ViewModel of this and then the ViewModel updates the Model.

Webservice

The Webservice serves as a layer to make sure that we can work with the tables and their entries from our database as objects in C#. When the client generates a request, the Webservice generates a response based on that request. All actions are requested using standard HTTP methods – GET, POST, PUT, PATCH, DELETE and the responses are returned as serialised JSON strings.

In order to work with relation data as objects we used the Entity Framework. The Entity Framework is an Object/Relational Mapping (ORM) framework that enables developers to work with relational data as domain-specific objects. Because we already had a database, we used the framework to automatically create the data access classes, but it can also be used to create a database from already existing classes. The WebAPI controllers that were automatically generated by the Entity Framework support the standard CRUD operations that allows us to Create, Read, Update and Delete data from the database. Because we needed to be able to CRUD sculptures associated with specific types of sculpture materials, we had to create our own controller. Figure 22 illustrates an action from one of our custom created controllers *SculptureMaterialController*. The action adds all materials related to a sculpture.

```

[Route("api/CreateSculptureMaterials/{sculptureId:int}")]
[HttpPost]
[ResponseType(typeof(void))]
public IHttpActionResult CreateSculptureMaterials(int sculptureId, List<int> materi-
alIds)
{
    const string sql = "INSERT INTO Sculpture_Material(Sculpture_ID, Material_ID)
VALUES(@P0, @P1)";
    var parameterList = new List<object>();
    foreach (var materialId in materialIds)
    {
        parameterList.Add(sculptureId);
        parameterList.Add(materialId);
        var parameters1 = parameterList.ToArray();
        _db.Database.ExecuteSqlCommand(sql, parameters1);
        parameterList.Clear();
    }
    _db.SaveChanges();

    return StatusCode(HttpStatusCode.NoContent);
}

```

Figure 22

The action is requested from *PersistenceFacade* when we ask the database to add all the materials for a newly created sculpture as shown in the following code.

```

        public async Task CreateSculptureMaterialsAsync(int sculptureId, List<int>
materialIds)
        {
            using (var client = new HttpClient(_handler))
            {
                client.BaseAddress = new Uri(ServerUrl);
                client.DefaultRequestHeaders.Clear();
                client.DefaultRequestHeaders.Accept.Add(new
MediaTyewithQualityHeaderValue("application/json"));

                var json = JsonConvert.SerializeObject(materialIds);

                var content = new StringContent(json, Encoding.UTF8, "Application/json");

                try
                {
                    var updateResponse = await
client.PostAsync("api/CreateSculptureMaterials/" + sculptureId, content);
                }
                catch (Exception ex)
                {
                    await new MessageDialog(ex.Message).ShowAsync();
                }
            }
        }
    }
}

```

Figure 23

GRASP

GRASP is an object oriented design principle used to help one understand the importance of object design and responsibility. The GRASP patterns, introduced by Craig Larman, are used to assign responsibilities to the objects. GRASP consists of nine patterns, but to keep this section short and on point only the ones relevant to our project are briefly described in the following. As soon as we were ready to start modelling and coding, we tried to apply this OO design principle and because we thought of the software objects as people with responsibilities it was a responsibility-driven design (RDD) process (Larman 2005, p. 277).

The Creator pattern

Larman's Creator pattern is concerned with who should have the responsibility of creating an instance of some class. In our project, this responsibility was given to the different ViewModels that create instances of sculptures and inspections if they need them.

Information Expert

Because our different ViewModels also know all information about sculptures, they can also be considered Information Experts.

The Controller pattern

This pattern deals with which 'layer' beyond the UI first receives and coordinates the system operations (Ibid. p. 287). For our project, we are using a use case controller, meaning that some of our controllers represent a use case scenario within which a system event occurs. For example, our *SulptureHandler* class illustrated below (*shown in Figure 24*) handles the use case scenarios of Creating, Updating and Deleting a sculpture. The purpose of the controller is to delegate and coordinate the necessary work without doing too much work itself. This goes hand-in-hand with another a Larman's principles of GRASP, Low Coupling.

```

namespace Sculpy.Handler
{
    public class SculptureHandler
    {
        public static async void DeleteSculpture(int id)
        {
            await new Persistancy.PersistenceFacade().DeleteSculptureAsync(id);
            SculpturesHandler.ResetCollectionAsync();
        }

        public static async void UpdateSculpture(Sculpture sculpture)
        {
            await new Persistancy.PersistenceFacade().UpdateSculptureAsync(sculpture);
            SculpturesHandler.ResetCollectionAsync();
        }

        public static async void CreateSculpture(Sculpture sculpture)
        {
            await new Persistancy.PersistenceFacade().CreateSculptureAsync(sculpture);
            SculpturesHandler.ResetCollectionAsync();
        }
    }
}

```

Figure 24

Low coupling

This principle is concerned with making sure there is low dependency between objects as well as an increased possibility of reusing the code. Because we created an MVVM application this principle was quite important and we believe we achieved it well. By ensuring that each view has its own ViewModel which is only focused on communicating the necessary information for the particular view. By assigning the responsibility in this way we have also achieved high cohesion.

Even though we tried to follow the GRASP principles, we found it practically difficult as confusion occurred because we noticed that multiple classes are Information Experts and the responsibility of creating instances are distributed around. This meant that Larman's nine GRASP principles were not as actively used and considered as they perhaps could have been.

Design Class Diagram

Figure 25

Contrary to the domain model, the class diagram shows the software classes. Class diagrams are notated using the UML notation. The class diagram shows all classes in the system as well as all properties and methods. The header is the class name, the next field is the properties and then the properties are the methods. The design class diagram is an important tool to create software. It creates

a good overview of how the structure of the program should look like as well as how the program already works if a developer needs to update the program later on.

We have made our Design Class Diagram using Visio and it is not completely true to the UML notation.

Correctly, the notation should go like so:

However, we have made it as such:

The reason was that when we created the design class diagram it seemed much easier to write it like it is written in the code. For ideal purposes, we should have stuck with the first method and done it with the right notation. In retrospective, we should have used the right notation from the beginning.

We created the class diagram after we made the software classes so in that sense it didn't help us much, however, it helps a lot when anyone wish to see the structure of the program as well as what methods and properties we have in our system.

System Sequence Diagrams

Figure 26

“A system sequence diagram (SSD) is a fast and easily created artefact that illustrates input and output events related to the systems under discussion” (Larman 2005, p.173)

A SSD shows system events generated by external actors. A SSD shows interaction between the actor and the system in a time order that follows the use case scenario (*shown in Figure 26*). A SSD is a picture that shows, for one particular scenario of a use case, events generated by external actors, their order, and inter-system events.

A SSD is an illustration of messages between the actor and the system. It shows messages, interactions or input from the user/actor and the response the system makes on that given interaction or input.

Our SSD is created based upon our use cases. We have made our SSD according to Larman’s practice and made sure we have traceability throughout the entire project. We have made our Design Sequence Diagrams (DSD) based upon the actor input made in the SSD. We have chosen to show a loop through

the CRUD operations as they can be looped through with nearly the same outcome. We have also chosen to show a loop at the draw report as you can continue to draw reports as long as the actor does the right input.

The SSD became an inspiration for our design sequence diagram. It served as a visual presentation of how our structured program should look, what input and output should be made.

Design Sequence Diagrams

Figure 27

A Design Sequence Diagram (DSD) is basically an interaction diagram (shown in Figure 27). The DSD is a great tool for OO design because you have to think through every method call, who they call and in what order.

A DSD starts with an external interaction (usually found in the SSD) and shows all page and/or classes that are involved in that interaction. The DSD shows all method calls and to what class in an order that goes to the right. Return messages go back and usually indicate a return statement. Arrows show the direction of the message call/return statement to the reader.

Our Design Sequence Diagram is made to be traceable. Our DSD are based upon our SSD. That means that the input methods come from our SSD and can be traced back all the way to our use cases.

We have chosen to do four DSDs, one for start-up – getting all sculptures from the database, one for creating a sculpture, one for creating an inspection and one for drawing out a report. These four are basically linked to our use cases. We have three use cases (CRUD sculpture, CRUD inspection and draw report) and chose to focus on the create part as they were similar.

Our DSD made inspiration for the flow of the code. We revised the DSD several times so it matches our code completely. It made code writing easier as we sort of knew.

Figure 28 – Draw Report

Figure 29 – Create Sculpture

Figure 30 – Create Inspection

Evaluating the Iterations

We started elaboration phase by doing an iteration plan where each iteration consisted of two weeks. From whiteboard sketches we made a table of artefacts and divided them into which was most important considering the timeline of the project. This table became our iteration plan. We have used Trello to organise the artefacts so everyone could see how far we were.

Week 13-14 - 1 st iteration of elaboration	Week 15-16 - 2 nd iteration
Core high risk use case	All diagrams
Core high risk architecture	Domain model
Refine requirements	Design class
Reduce risk	System sequence
Prototype on paper	Interaction diagram
Iteration plan	Glossary
	Implement high risk use cases
	Implement test
	GitHub

Week 17-18 – 3 rd iteration of elaboration	Week 19-20 -4 th iteration
Implement high risk use cases	Refine diagrams
Implement high risk architecture	Glossary
Iteration plan	Unit test
Navigation in the program	Refine report
Implement map	Implement all use cases
Filtering and sorting	
Sculpture page and selected sculpture	
Settings page	
Refine report	
Meeting with supervisor	

Week 21 – 5 th iteration of elaboration
Pair programming (go through)
Revise
Finish report

As with the inception phase, we made a Gant chart containing all the artefacts that needed to be done. The Gant chart gave us a good visual overview of all the artefacts and their delivery time.

The only part of our plan that went over schedule was implementing the CRUD operations. We had estimated that the CRUD operations would be done by the 10th of May but reality showed that we were still working on them until the very last week of the project. This made going to the construction

phase impossible for us, as we had not finished the core architecture or high-risk use cases of our product.

Construction

Code Walkthrough – Delete a sculpture

1. The user presses the “Delete Sculpture” button on the UI which starts the deletion process.

2. In the code, the click event is triggered when the user clicks the button.

```
<CommandBar.SecondaryCommands>  
  <AppBarButton Label="Delete sculpture" Click="DeleteSculptureButton_OnClick"/>  
</CommandBar.SecondaryCommands>
```

3. In the associated method we determine the dialog box to pop-out for ensuring that the user didn't accidentally press it.

```
/// <summary>  
/// This method will show the dialog box when the user wants to delete a sculpture.  
/// </summary>  
/// <param name="sender"></param>  
/// <param name="e"></param>  
1 reference | Daniel-Simionescu, 1 day ago | 2 authors, 4 changes  
private async void DeleteSculptureButton_OnClick(object sender, RoutedEventArgs e)  
{  
    DeleteSculptureContentDialog.Visibility = Visibility.Visible;  
    ContentDialogResult result = await DeleteSculptureContentDialog.ShowAsync();  
    DeleteSculptureContentDialog = null;  
    await Task.Delay(TimeSpan.FromSeconds(5));  
    GoBack();  
}
```

4. If it's intentional, then the user is going to press the “delete” button.

5. An associated method is associated with the click event for the primary button.

```
<ContentDialog Name="DeleteSculptureContentDialog"
  Visibility="Collapsed" VerticalAlignment="Center"
  Grid.Column="1"
  Background="{ThemeResource SystemControlBackgroundAccentBrush}"
  Title="DELETE SCULPTURE"
  PrimaryButtonText="delete"
  Foreground="Black"
  FontWeight="ExtraLight"
  SecondaryButtonText="cancel"
  BorderBrush="White"
  BorderThickness="1"
  PrimaryButtonClick="Click_OnClick">
  <StackPanel>
    <TextBlock Text="Are you sure you want to delete this sculpture from the list?"
      FontSize="16" Foreground="Black" FontWeight="ExtraLight"
      TextWrapping="Wrap"></TextBlock>
  </StackPanel>
</ContentDialog>
```

6. In this trigger we are going to call the 'Delete Sculpture' method from the Handler class related to a Sculpture. We are passing only the associated ID of that sculpture which is taken from the ViewModel. Also we remove the sculpture from the Catalog which contains all the sculptures and we navigate back to the Homepage.

```
/// <summary>
/// This method is connected to the Delete Sculpture button.
/// </summary>
/// <param name="sender"></param>
/// <param name="args"></param>
1 reference | Daniel-Simionescu, 1 day ago | 1 author, 1 change
private async void Click_OnClick(ContentDialog sender, ContentDialogButtonClickEventArgs args)
{
    await SculptureHandler.DeleteSculpture(ViewModel.PassedSculpture.ID);
    SculptureCatalogSingleton.Instance.Sculptures.Remove(ViewModel.PassedSculpture);
    GoBack();
}
```

7. As commented in the C# code, in order to fully delete a sculpture from the Database, we need to remove any of its instances. So we created four method in the Persistence Facade which send requests to some custom Actions in the Controllers from the Web Service, which are called with the related ID of the sculpture.

```

/// <summary>
/// In this method we delete a sculpture from the database.
/// We treated also the scenario when there are references related to a sculpture which is going to be deleted,
/// ,so we had to take care of all its references across the tables in the database.
/// </summary>
/// <param name="id">In order to delete a sculpture we need to have only its ID.</param>
/// <returns></returns>
2 references | Daniel-Simionescu, 1 day ago | 1 author, 3 changes
public static async Task DeleteSculpture(int id)
{
    await new Persistancy.PersistencyFacade().DeleteSculptureTypesAsync(id);
    await new Persistancy.PersistencyFacade().DeleteSculptureMaterialsAsync(id);
    await new Persistancy.PersistencyFacade().DeleteSculptureInspectionsAsync(id);
    await new Persistancy.PersistencyFacade().DeleteSculptureAsync(id);
}

```

8. We are going to show only one of the methods from the Persistency Facade due to the fact that they are quite similar. In this method we send a request to the Web Service and the Action will be a *'delete'*, so we are calling it with the DeleteAsync method and we are also passing the ID of the sculpture.

```

/// <summary>
/// This method is called when a sculpture is deleted in order to remove any reference from the Database of a sculpture before we delete it.
/// </summary>
/// <param name="id">This parameter holds the value of the Sculpture which is going to be deleted.</param>
/// <returns></returns>
1 reference | Daniel-Simionescu, 1 day ago | 1 author, 1 change
public async Task DeleteSculptureInspectionsAsync(int id)
{
    using (var client = new HttpClient(_handler))
    {
        client.BaseAddress = new Uri(ServerUrl);
        client.DefaultRequestHeaders.Clear();
        client.DefaultRequestHeaders.Accept.Add(new MediaTypeWithQualityHeaderValue("application/json"));

        try
        {
            var response = await client.DeleteAsync("api/DeleteInspectionForSculpture/" + id);
        }
        catch (Exception ex)
        {
            await new MessageDialog(ex.Message).ShowAsync();
        }
    }
}

```

9. This is a HttpDelete action which searches for any inspection that has a reference to the sculpture which is going to be deleted and it removes them from the collection of Inspections

```

/// <summary>
/// This Action deletes all the inspections for a specific sculpture.
/// </summary>
/// <param name="sculptureId">We need to pass only the ID of the sculpture.</param>
/// <returns></returns>
[Route("api/DeleteInspectionForSculpture/{sculptureId:int}")]
[HttpDelete]
[ResponseType(typeof(void))]
0 references | Daniel-Simionescu, 1 day ago | 1 author, 1 change
public IActionResult DeleteInspectionForSculpture(int sculptureId)
{
    foreach (var insp in db.Inspections.Where(inspection => inspection.Sculpture_ID == sculptureId))
    {
        db.Inspections.Remove(insp);
    }
    db.SaveChanges();

    return StatusCode(HttpStatusCode.NoContent);
}

```

10. After all the references of that specific sculpture are removed for both the Types and Materials Linking tables, the sculpture will be successfully deleted from the database. The user will be taken back to the Homepage.

Testing

Black box testing (also called functional testing) is testing that ignores the internal mechanism of a system or component and focuses solely on the outputs generated in response to selected inputs and execution conditions. (MSDN, 2016)

White box testing (also called structural testing and glass box testing) is testing that takes into account the internal mechanism of a system or component.

Unit Testing

Unit testing is the testing of individual software units or groups of related units which verifies that the code does what it is intended to do at a very low structural level.

We created an individual program which tests a single unit/part of the software. This type of testing is performed by using the White Box Testing method (shown in Figure 31 and 32).

```
[TestMethod]
0 references | Daniel-Simionescu, 5 days ago | 1 author, 1 change
public void TestNormalId()
{
    //Arrange
    _sculptureId = 7;

    //Act
    _testSculpture.ID = _sculptureId;

    //Assert
    Assert.AreEqual(_sculptureId, _testSculpture.ID);
}
```

Figure 31

Figure 32

We chose to focus on the tests that had the biggest impact on the behavior of the system.

Throughout all the test methods we applied the AAA (Arrange, Act, and Assert) Pattern. We performed data validation for all the possible inputs.

How did it help us?

- The code became easily changeable because we were able to catch the defects while they appeared.
- We saved time for development because we found and fixed defects early.
- Debugging was easy too, because when something failed, we needed to look back only over the last few changes.
- And the most important thing is that our code became reliable.

Integration Testing

Integration testing is a logical extension of unit testing.

Unit tests enable you to catch many defects. However, a limitation of unit tests is their inability to detect errors that occur across external boundaries. This situation can include when there are databases, other services, or even flat files. It is important to create tests that validate this functionality, and this is why integration tests are important. They verify service methods when all of the dependencies are in place.

We are testing different parts of the system in isolation, using the Black Box Testing method.

We verified how the components interact with each other.

We checked the HTTP requests and XML or JSON responses generated by the components (*shown in Figure 33 and 34*).

Integration Testing for the CLIENT:

Test Case	Test Steps	Test Data	Web Request	Status
Create a new sculpture.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch the application. 2. Select the add sculpture button. 3. Add the name and address for the sculpture. 4. Select the associated placement, types and materials. 5. Click accept button to create the sculpture. 	Name: Skulptur Address: Eriksvej 4, Roskilde Placement: Building Types: Fountain Material: Marble Cultural-heritage: A	<pre>POST http://skulptwebapi.azurewebsites.net/Api/Sculptures HTTP/1.1 Accept: application/json Content-Length: 379 Content-Type: application/json; charset=utf-8 Host: skulptwebapi.azurewebsites.net Connection: Keep-Alive Pragma: no-cache Cookie: ARRAffinity=b1183e72feb1c6fd5567fd97092d41e96d94854eac1c9c1 {"ID":259,"Sculpture_Name":"Skulptur","Sculpture_Placement":"Bygning"}</pre>	Passed
Delete an existing sculpture.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch the application. 2. Select a sculpture from the list. 3. Click on the delete button. 4. Click on the accept button from the new pop-out window. 	-	<pre>DELETE http://skulptwebapi.azurewebsites.net/api/Sculptures/211 HTTP/1.1 Accept: application/json Host: skulptwebapi.azurewebsites.net Content-Length: 0 Connection: Keep-Alive Pragma: no-cache Cookie: ARRAffinity=5c6d2abfb4d85e35d2f7731aec647f24ab1a2538870a1e054792d</pre>	Passed
Create a new inspection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch the application. 2. Select a sculpture from the list. 3. Click on the add new inspection button. 4. Add the name and the description for the inspection. 4. Select the associated date, damage, treatment and frequency. 5. Click accept button to create the inspection. 	Name: General Inspection Description: This sculpture needs urgent washing. Date: 16-05-2016 Damage: Discoloration Treatment: Wash Frequency: Weekly.	<pre>PUT http://skulptwebapi.azurewebsites.net/Api/CreateInspectionForSculpture/1 HTTP/1.1 Accept: application/json Content-Length: 267 Content-Type: application/json; charset=utf-8 Host: skulptwebapi.azurewebsites.net Connection: keep-alive Pragma: no-cache Cookie: ARRAffinity=b1183e72feb1c6fd5567fd97092d41e96d94854eac1c9cb3eb1df01bbd89709; {"ID":4,"Inspection_Date":"2016-05-16T00:00:00","Inspection_Note":"This sculpture ne</pre>	Passed
Update an existing inspection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch the application. 2. Select a sculpture from the list. 3. Select an inspection from the list. 4. Click on the edit inspection. 5. Change the desired details. 6. Click the accept button. 	Name: Updated Inspection Description: This sculpture needs urgent cleaning. Date: 16-05-2016 Damage: Discoloration Treatment: Wash Frequency: Weekly.	<pre>PUT http://skulptwebapi.azurewebsites.net/api/Inspections/119 HTTP/1.1 Accept: application/json Content-Length: 270 Content-Type: application/json; charset=utf-8 Host: skulptwebapi.azurewebsites.net Connection: Keep-Alive Pragma: no-cache Cookie: ARRAffinity=b1183e72feb1c6fd5567fd97092d41e96d94854eac1c9cb3eb {"ID":119,"Inspection_Date":"2016-05-16T00:00:00","Inspection_Note":"T</pre>	Passed

Figure 33

Test case	Preconditions	Test Steps	Test Data	Expected Result	Actual Results
Create a new sculpture.	The internet access is required for retrieving the future ID of the newly created sculpture and also for sending the sculpture to the Web Service.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch the application. 2. Select the add sculpture button. 3. Add the name and address for the sculpture. 4. Select the associated placement, types and materials. 5. Click accept button to create the sculpture. 	Name: Skulptur Address: Eriksvej 4 Placement: Building Types: Fountain Material: Marble Cultural-heritage: A	The sculpture is created and it is stored for future retrieving.	IsSuccessCode: true StatusCode: Created
Create new sculpture.	The internet access is required for retrieving the future ID of the newly created sculpture and also for sending the sculpture to the Web Service.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch the application. 2. Select the add sculpture button. 3. Add the name and address. 4. Select the associated placement, types and materials. 5. Click accept button to create the sculpture. 	Address: Eriksvej 4 Types: Fountain Material: Marble Cultural-heritage: A	The sculpture won't be created due to the fact that it lacks some specifications, specifically the name and placement properties.	IsSuccessCode: false StatusCode: Bad Request
Create new inspection.	The internet access is required for retrieving the future ID of the newly created inspection and also for sending the inspection to the Web Service.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch the application. 2. Select a sculpture from the list. 3. Click on the add inspection button. 4. Add the name and the description for the inspection. 4. Select the associated date, damage, treatment and frequency. 5. Click accept button to create the inspection. 	Name: General Inspection Description: This sculpture needs urgent washing. Date: 16-05-2016 Damage: Dirt Treatment: Wash Frequency: Weekly.	The inspection is created and it is stored for future retrieving.	IsSuccessCode: true StatusCode: Created
Delete existing sculpture.	The internet access is required for retrieving the future ID of the newly created sculpture and also for sending the sculpture to the Web Service.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch the application. 2. Select a sculpture from the list. 3. Click on the delete button. 4. Click on the accept button from the new pop-out window. 	Nothing	The sculpture was deleted and it is no longer stored on the server. Also the list sculptures was refreshed.	IsSuccessCode: true StatusCode: OK
Update an existing inspection.	The internet access is required for also sending the inspection to the Web Service.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Launch the application. 2. Select a sculpture from the list. 3. Select an inspection from the list. 4. Click on the edit inspection. 5. Change the desired details. 6. Click the accept button. 	Name: Updated Inspection Description: This sculpture needs urgent washing. Date: 16-05-2016 Damage: Dirt Treatment: Wash Frequency: Weekly.	The inspection is updated and it is stored for future retrieving.	IsSuccessCode: true StatusCode: OK

Figure 35

Conclusion

Evaluation of the Project and the Product

The Unified Process framework used together with iterative development greatly helped us to manage, plan and carry out the development from the early stages of Business Analysis to the deployment of a functional prototype. However, we did encounter challenges and, among other things, had to realize that we should have focused on the artifacts which added value to our analysis and design.

Since C# is such a popular and widely used programming language, we found it easy to obtain documentations and resources which greatly helped us overcome challenges throughout the development process. Moreover C# is a strongly typed, Object-Oriented language which provided code reusability when we implemented the features of the software.

At the beginning we believed that the old existing database could easily be migrated into the new system we developed, but later on we recognized and had to admit that this was not possible. This meant that we had to adjust, and look for another solution.

As the challenges arose, we were meant to be able to adapt to changing requirements, and partly succeeded to do so, but we found it really difficult due to the lack of communication with the client and thus the end-user.

We managed to have a functional product at the end of each phase, even though we had to partly abandon some of our goals for the current iteration. We accomplished this by rescheduling our iteration plans when it was necessary. We are satisfied with our product, even though we did not manage to get a fully functional product, only just a functional prototype.

As regarding the future perspectives for our software, we would require to gain much more knowledge about databases, cloud services and C# programming language.

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Appendices

Appendix 2: Notes from the presentation of the company

Notes
 Tuesday, February 23, 2016 12:58 PM

Notes from presentation 23/02

Mission:
 She gathers information about sculptures for Copenhagen Municipality by going around the city to take notes and collect specific information on every sculpture.

Taking care of sculptures:
 Municipality of Copenhagen. What is the condition for the sculptures and does the municipality use this as a tool?

The Sculpture's Attributes:
 Name
 Number
 Address
 Material (stone, metal, wood, etc)
 Damages (if it is on the sculpture or on its base)
 Cost
 Time for restoration
 Notes (treatment history, backlog)
 Treatments needed (immediate, within next 20 years)
 Cultural value (in Copenhagen, local, international)

Wishes/extra requirements for the app:

- Quick overview page
- Photos to upload for identification purpose
- Map and maybe GPS
- Online connection
- Average cost calculator
- Different permission level (access) for tourist
- Notification to admin by users about damages
- Surrounding area (gardening, cutting trees...)

Questions for EVA:

- How do you define "reports"? What is it? Who is for?
- How do you "navigate" the value to A, B, C (high, medium, low) from existing one (much more options: cultural heritage, historical stuff...)

Database related ideas:

Synchronized with the whole database.
 All the old database should be migrated to the new system.

GUI related ideas:

Autosuggest box
 Grid View
 Flexible, intuitive
 Images Linked to damages.
 Maps
 Overviews, sorting

Should we have a possibility to see previous damages on each sculpture? So we can see that on a certain date this damage was fixed by this person?
 Should we have map?
 Should it be a specific app about the sculptures that then has admin logic where the interface now offers options for adding entries on the state and condition of the different sculptures.
 Aalborg has a similar project - they have map

Business:
 Value: Tourists love making trips here to see the different buildings and sculptures
 Threats: Other conservators are starting to do the same. Also people from Sweden.
 Unprofessional offering clearing for low price, but in risk of damaging the stones etc.
 Opportunities: (Sweden, Norway)
 Strength: She has already built quite a big database.
 Customers: Currently only Copenhagen.
 Future: Slagelse, Kalundborg, Roskilde

The cost of those remedies. The prices are overall per sculpture.

Competition: maybe possible partners.

Multiple people usage:
 Strength: The only company in this field.

Weakness:
 A small income.

Threats:
 Other from Sweden.
 Clearing companies.
 The municipality has no money.

Opportunity:
 Other countries.
 New business partners.
 Minister of Tourism.

Working with København Kommune (might expand to Kalundborg, Roskilde etc.)
 - Partners: Independent contractors
 - Cost is only time and materials.
 - Revenue is from København Kommune.

It's a coming-up market. Not that many competitors but there can be.
 - Sculpture restoration workshop -> trying to become partners.

Strength -> the one who started doing it. One other person doing it for Aalborg Kommune. Eva has a lot of experience in the field. Has a big database of sculpture.
Weakness -> a small world. Not so much money in the field.
Opportunity -> the municipality is starting to see the importance of their sculptures and cultural heritage
Threats -> New entrants in the market.

Is a conservator (taking care of cultural heritage) specially sculptures and building facades?

Has a project for all outdoor sculptures.
Already has a database

Goes by bike and find the sculptures and notes the conditions. Makes a registration if she find damage.

Steps in current system.

- Basic info needed: Name, id, address, what surface (building ground etc.), Material: Brick, wood, stone, bronze, etc.
- Damage:
 8 different kind - doesn't like the current way to do it - What would she prefer there?
 The 8 kinds of damages are the most common damages.
- Cultural value:
 She selects cultural value from A, B and C. to have a priority of which is most important to fix first. So basically a way of prioritizing the repairs.
- Recommendation for treatment:
 Acute or can wait...
 She also states how often it should be cleaned or treated. When does the sculpture need to be looked at again.
- Notes:
 How does it look, where is the damage, what needs to be done. Basically a treatment history with brief info.

Should we have a possibility to see previous damages on each sculpture? So we can see that on a certain date this damage was fixed by this person?
 Should we have map?
 Should it be a specific app about the sculptures that then has admin logic where the interface now offers options for adding entries on the state and condition of the different sculptures.
 Aalborg has a similar project - they have map

Business:
 Value: Tourists love making trips here to see the different buildings and sculptures
 Threats: Other conservators are starting to do the same. Also people from Sweden.
 Unprofessional offering clearing for low price, but in risk of damaging the stones etc.
 Opportunities: (Sweden, Norway)
 Strength: She has already built quite a big database.
 Customers: Currently only Copenhagen.
 Future: Slagelse, Kalundborg, Roskilde

Appendix 3: Meetings with the stakeholder

Reports

- Export them to pdf format and send them directly via email services
- Sorting/Select treatment & Select Damage => to be able to select more type at the same time dropdown => checkbox?
- To be able to select what the reports will include (who's the report for?)
- List of inspections should include just type of damage and treatment

Damage

- Predefined damages: yes!
- Predefined treatments? Yes! BUT also an option to input unique ones and deeper descriptions (sub/other => include it in inspection notes maybe? SHE WILL CHECK THE REGULAR ONES
- **between these above NO association, LOOSE COUPLING**

Address

- Later on when she is at the given sculpture => edit sculpture => ADD LOCATION/Update on MAP

??

- Some treatment and frequency like " regular wash" done this year => when to be done NEXT TIME? Include that
- Search for treatment: see in 2017, 2018: list of needs to be done
- Wash, wax..
- Cultural Heritage Value: 1 - 2 - 3 (and why: she will decide and notify us later on)

Brief notes from meeting 1

Brief notes from meeting 2

Appendix 4: Meetings with the supervisors

Meeting with Poul

Thursday 5 May 2016 08:06

When do we get the missing information (treatment types frequently used etc.) from Eva?

- Poul will find out soon - for now we should just use dummy data like "Treatment 1", "Treatment 2" and so on

TR

How do we get information from linking tables

- Poul is still working on an efficient solution, but he showed us a way to do it and promised to share the code with Daniel.

TR

How do we migrate the old database?

- We shouldn't worry about migrating the existing database to our new solution. We should just insert some data into all tables and make sure that it works (can add, edit, delete inspections + sculptures)

TR

Should we make unit test - if so, how many?

- No need to unit test everything. Just make a few to demonstrate that we know how to use them

Other notes from the meeting

- We need to update and stick to our iteration plans
- The report should have a section on Test planning (Maybe just half a page?). And after iteration write about how we tested (Unit, Usability etc) and what we found. Doesn't have to be long - just a few lines, Poul said.
- Longitude and Latitude columns could be included in Sculptures table and just leave Zip code and city in a table of its own. We need to look at this together Monday and make a decision

Appendix 5: Project Report

WHICH PARTS:			WHO?	
Introduction			✓ Istvan	
Vision for the Project	Project Objectives		✓ Istvan	
	Problem Definition		✓ ALL	
Analysis of Business	The Company		✓ Istvan	
	Business Analysis Artefacts	The Business Model Canvas	✓ Istvan	
		SWOT Analysis	✓ Istvan	
		Porter's Five Forces	✓ Istvan	
Business Product Vision		✓ Istvan		
The Project – Sculpy	The Project – Sculpy	Project Establishment	Human Resources	✓ Istvan
			Technology Resources	✓ Istvan
			Group Contract	✓ Istvan
			List of Risks and Management Plan	✓ Istvan
			Project Management	✓ Istvan
			Overall Plan	✓ Istvan
			Quality Factors	✓ Istvan
Inception	Requirements	Use Cases	✓ Istvan	
	Use Case Diagram		✓ Casper	
	GUI – PoP		✓ Toke	
	Planning the Iterations		✓ Casper	
Elaboration	Domain Model		✓ Casper	
	Entity Relationship Modelling		✓ Toke	
	Core Architecture Diagram		✓ Toke	
	Design Class Diagram		✓ Casper	
	Design Sequence Diagrams		✓ Casper	
	System Sequence Diagrams		✓ Casper	
	Planning the Iterations		✓ Casper	
Construction			✓ Daniel	
Conclusion	Evaluation of the Project		✓ ALL	
Literature List			✓ ALL	
	Glossary		✓ ALL	
	Presentation of the company		✓ Istvan	
	Meetings with the stakeholder		✓ Istvan	
	Meetings with Supervisors		✓ Istvan	
	Report Documentation		✓ ALL	